

MEDICAL SCIENCES

FACTORS DETERMINING THE LEVEL OF PATIENT SATISFACTION AT THE STAGES OF COMPLEX TREATMENT OF DENTITION AND OCCLUSION DEFORMITIES

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Abstract

Deformations of the dentition are a frequent complication of defects in the dentition, and this pathology cannot always be eliminated only by orthopedic means. In these cases, complex treatment of deformities is carried out - orthopedic treatment in combination with surgical treatment. In most cases, the treatment of this pathology must be approached comprehensively; only then can good treatment results be achieved and possible complications prevented.

Keywords: secondary deformations of the dentition and bite, complex treatment.

Patient satisfaction with dental prosthetics for deformities of the dentition and bite is individual and often unpredictable for an orthopedic dentist [1, 5, 9]. Untimely treatment of this pathology, leading to significant morphological, functional, aesthetic changes and affecting the psycho-emotional status of patients, already has a significant impact on the level of satisfaction with the treatment result [4, 7, 8, 10]. Therefore, timely diagnosis, prediction and treatment of dental deformities in adults is important in orthopedic dentistry [2, 3, 6].

The purpose of the study is to identify factors that determine the level of patient satisfaction at the stages of complex treatment of dentition and occlusion deformities.

Material and methods. We carried out complex treatment and examined 47 patients aged 35 to 49 years with deformities of the dentition and bite. In order to identify the factors that determine the level of satisfaction with the results of treatment, indicators of the functional state were studied at each stage of treatment using the SAN and MLO "Adaptability" methods. The degree of involvement of patients' experiences and changes in personal relationships associated with existing pathology and various manifestations of life activity was determined based on the results of a self-assessment questionnaire that we developed. The questionnaire took into account such functional states as activity, well-being, mood, sleep, appetite, attitude towards illness and treatment, towards one's future, work (study), relationships with others and relatives, satisfaction with one's appearance, etc. The study of patients was carried out at all stages of complex treatment: before, during and after orthodontic correction, before and after prosthetics. In order to connect the study characteristics of the functional state of patients at each stage with the final result of treatment, which is designated as EC (an external criterion for the effectiveness of the treatment measures taken), a factor analysis of

the studied indicators was carried out. The role of indicators of the functional state of patients in the formation of VC at each stage of treatment was determined by regression analysis followed by the presentation of a predictive equation.

Results. According to the results of factor analysis, at each stage of complex treatment, on average, 5-6 main factors were identified that influenced the patient's self-esteem, which from 72.0 to 81% determined the manifestations of all studied signs. One of the significant factors influencing the patient's self-esteem at almost all stages of complex treatment is the perception of teeth, bite and attractiveness of the smile. The following less significant, but no less important factors include the idea of the future, in particular about the outcome of treatment, external relationships, internal experiences in connection with the evaluative perception of the external appearance of the patients' environment, experiences associated with possible difficulties in treatment and insufficient attention from others loved ones. Depending on the stage of treatment, the priority of self-esteem indicators changed. Thus, before the start of complex treatment, factor analysis showed that the studied characteristics formed 6 statistically significant factors, which determine 79% of their manifestations. The first factor, which determines the manifestation of the studied signs by 17%, includes the indicators most closely related to IC - assessment of teeth, bite and attractiveness of the smile. The remaining 5 factors carry a smaller load - 14, 13, 9, 8 and 11%, respectively, and characterize the idea of the future, external relationships, internal experiences in connection with the evaluative perception of the external appearance of the patients' environment, experiences associated with possible difficulties in treatment and insufficient manifestation attention to your loved ones. At the stage of orthodontic treatment, the influence of the studied signs decreased to 76% and to 72% after its completion and the start of orthopedic treatment. Significant factors

were the assessment of the patients' relationship with the external environment and the evaluative perception of teeth, bite and smile attractiveness in 16%. Factor 3 (10%) includes indicators characterizing hope for a favorable outcome of treatment and its impact on the nature of relationships with other people. The remaining factors included internal experiences related to relationships with family and friends (4th factor, with 16% influence on the manifestation of all signs), with possible difficulties in treatment (5th factor, 8% influence); internal experiences that determine communication needs (6th factor, 10% influence). The developed mathematical forecast model showed that before treatment, the value of VC in patients is influenced by assessments of appearance, teeth, occlusion and prospects for the success of treatment; during orthodontic treatment, assessment of occlusion lost its important role, giving way to expectations of a more attractive smile and maintaining the importance of assessing one's external appearance and prospects for success of further treatment. After orthodontic treatment before prosthetics, a mathematical model for predicting the value of VC showed that its elements are the same as those that were before complex treatment. After completion of orthopedic treatment, the structure of 6 statistically significant factors changed little. As before, the elements that determine the evaluative attitude of teeth, bite and smile attractiveness turned out to be the most associated with IC. It should be noted that the level of influence of the identified main factors on the assessment of results after prosthetics increased to 81%. The resulting mathematical model showed that the value of VC is influenced by the parameters of smile attractiveness assessed by patients, as well as changes in appearance after treatment. The level of reliability of mathematical forecast models ($p < 0.001$) and information content ($R_1 = 0.97$) is high. Analysis of the results of the study of patients showed that the external data of a person are emotionally and socially significant characteristics that influence their perception of the results of treatment. At the same time, other less significant, but no less important parameters under study also significantly affect the self-esteem of patients, which requires conducting a focused conversation between the doctor and patients during the treatment process, aimed at preventing and reducing susceptibility to value judgments about the intermediate results of treatment on the part of others.

Conclusion.

The level of patient satisfaction at the stages of complex treatment of dental deformities determines the tone and severity of their experiences against the background of situational anxiety associated with hopes for successful treatment. Timely prediction of significant factors influencing the patient's self-esteem will have a significant positive impact on the level of satisfaction with the treatment.

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